

Template - Processing analysis

Template to process all surfaces acquired with the LSM with the 50x/0.75 and 50x/0.95 objectives.

Processing

Identity card			
Name:	Kremasti4_LSM_50x_type2_b_Topo		
Created on:	4/13/2021 4:38:37 PM		
Studiabile type:	Surface		
Axis:	X		
Length:	255.5	µm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Axis:	Y		
Length:	255.5	µm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Axis:	Z		
Layer type:	Topography		
Length:	18.74	µm	
Size:	65532	digits	
Spacing:	0.2860	nm	
NM-points ratio:	0.000 % (0 Pts)		

Identity card			
Name:	Kremasti4_LSM_50x_t...filtered (As 2.500 μm)		
File path:	D:\...\Kremasti4_LSM_50x_type2_b_Topo.sur		
Created on:	4/13/2021 4:38:37 PM		
Studiable type:	Surface		
Axis:	X		
Length:	255.5	μm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Offset:	0.000	μm	
Axis:	Y		
Length:	255.5	μm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Offset:	-255.5	μm	
Axis:	Z		
Layer type:	Topography		
Length:	3.329	μm	
Min:	-2.082	μm	
Max:	1.247	μm	
Size:	116426	digits	
Spacing:	0.0286	nm	
NM-points ratio:	3.158 % (284199 Pts)		

Identity card			
Name:	Kremasti4_LSM_50x_ty...in non-measured points		
Created on:	4/13/2021 4:38:37 PM		
Studiable type:	Surface		
Axis:	X		
Length:	255.5	μm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Axis:	Y		
Length:	255.5	μm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Axis:	Z		
Layer type:	Topography		
Length:	3.329	μm	
Size:	116426	digits	
Spacing:	0.0286	nm	
NM-points ratio:	0.000 % (0 Pts)		

Analyses

8. ISO 25178-2 parameters on surface #7

ISO 25178 - Primary surface			
<i>F: [Workflow] Form removed (LS-poly 3)</i>			
<i>S-filter (λ_s): [Workflow] S-filtered (λ_s 2.500 μm)</i>			
Height parameters			
Sq	0.3344	μm	
Ssk	-0.9943		
Sku	7.071		
Sp	1.242	μm	
Sv	2.087	μm	
Sz	3.329	μm	
Sa	0.2395	μm	
Functional parameters			
Smr	21.11	%	
Smc	0.3684	μm	
Sxp	0.8096	μm	
Spatial parameters			
Sal	28.43	μm	
Str	0.7058		
Std	39.25	$^\circ$	
Hybrid parameters			
Sdq	0.1134		
Sdr	0.6012	%	
Functional parameters (Volume)			
Vm	0.01569	$\mu\text{m}^3/\mu\text{m}^2$	
Vv	0.3841	$\mu\text{m}^3/\mu\text{m}^2$	
Vmp	0.01569	$\mu\text{m}^3/\mu\text{m}^2$	
Vmc	0.2411	$\mu\text{m}^3/\mu\text{m}^2$	
Vvc	0.3320	$\mu\text{m}^3/\mu\text{m}^2$	
Vvv	0.05213	$\mu\text{m}^3/\mu\text{m}^2$	

Analyses:	
ISO 25178	8.
Furrow	9.
Texture direction	10.
Texture isotropy	11.
SSFA	12.

9. Furrow analysis on surface #7

All furrows are shown.

Parameters	Value	Unit
Maximum depth of furrows	2.238	µm
Mean depth of furrows	0.2734	µm
Mean density of furrows	4250	cm/cm2

10. Texture direction on surface #7

Parameters	Value	Unit
First direction	180.0	°
Second direction	44.99	°
Third direction	135.0	°

11. Texture isotropy on surface #7

Parameters	Value	Unit
Texture isotropy	69.67	%

12. SSFA on surface #7

